
TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY IN ARTISANAL FISHERIES (AF) IN BADAGRY LOCAL GOVERNMENT
AREA OF LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the technical efficiency in artisanal fisheries in Lagos State of Nigeria. The study employed a two stage random sampling procedure for the selection of 120 respondents. The analytical techniques involved descriptive statistics and estimation of technical efficiency following maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) procedure available in FRONTIER 4.1. The MLE result of the stochastic frontier production function showed that hired labour, cost of repair and capital items are critical factors that influence productivity of artisanal fishermen with the coefficient of hired labour being highly elastic. This implies that employing more labour will significantly increase the catch in the study area. The predicted farm efficiency with an average value of 0.92 showed that there is a marginal potential of about 8 percent to increase the catch, hence the income of the fishermen. The study further examined the factors that influence productivity of fishermen in the study area. Year of education, mode of operation and frequency of fishing have important implication on the technical efficiency of fishermen in the study area.

KEYWORDS: maximum likelihood estimation , artisanal fisheries , productivity , Lagos State

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, different governments in Nigeria have recognized the relevance of the fisheries sub – sectors, which are composed of the marine, brackish and freshwater. Several attempts were made over the years to boost their productivity through institutional reforms and the various fiscal and economic measures. Some of these measures provided tax exemption and input subsidy schemes for distribution to fishermen to stimulate increased production. Despite all these forms of external intervention in the development plans, the fisheries sector still showed a deficit in the supply and demand of fish to the population (Jinadu, 2000).

Artisanal fishing has been popular since the colonial era until the era of industrial fishing in the 70s and 80s. During those times, artisanal fishing constituted a high percentage of fish in Lagos and Nigeria as a whole. Artisanal fisheries, a term recognized by the FAO and other international agencies, refer to small scale fisheries involved in a diverse continuum of activities (Demuynck, 1994) with the use of simple technology for the exploitation of fishery resources in aquatic medium such as rivers, lagoons, lake, ocean and coastal water not beyond the nautical miles of the nation’s territorial water. (Williams, 1988

The role of the fisheries sector, particularly small scale artisanal fisheries as prime mover in the economic of fishers in coastal communities is very well known. However, with increase in world fish production, employment in the fishery sector has also increased tremendously. According to FAO (2002), an estimated 35 million people were directly engaged in fishing and fish farming either as a full – time or part – time occupation in year 2000 with 2.59 million of them in Africa. The growing number of people which depends on fisheries exploitation put such natural resources under severe strain, leading to over exploitation and consequently depletion.

Artisanal fishing is often, but not always, less intensive and less stressful on fish populations than modern industrial fishing techniques. It is subject to difficulties in the export process due to inadequate investment in refrigeration and processing facilities. (Wikipedia, 2009). However, artisanal fishery has continued to dominate the fisheries, contributing over 80% of total fish production. The inland water and coastal seas are fully exploited and the increase in fishery production is not likely (Nwafili and Gao, 2007).

For the entire artisanal coastal and inland sectors, fishing is the major source of livelihood. A total of 700,000 fishermen (500,000 coastal and 200,000 inland) are recorded as primary producers. For such a well - integrated industry, total employment could well be five – fold. (FCWC, 2010).

According to Amire (2003), the main reason attributed to the fall in the number of canoes, both motorized and non – motorized, was the rise on the cost of fishing inputs from 1984 to 1993. This was occasioned by the withdrawal of the 50 percent subsidy on fishing inputs hitherto given by government and the fall in the value of the Nigerian currency due to the global economic recession, which made the price of imported items including fishing inputs prohibitive. Fishermen who are mainly rural based lack collateral, and credit facilities were not readily available to enable them procure the inputs at the prevailing market prices.

Currently the Nigerian fishing industry is in dynamic state. There is over – capitalization in the industrial fleet; over fishing of the coastal resources, declining catch, both in quantity and especially in quality, environmental degradation seriously impeding the productivity of the artisanal sector; and declining efficiency due to lack of technical innovation.

Efficiency measurement has received considerable attention from both theoretical and applied economists. From a theoretical point of view, there has been a spirited exchange on the relative importance of the various components of firm efficiency (Leibenstein, 1966). From the applied perspective, measuring efficiency is important because this is the first step in a process that might lead to substantial resource savings. These resource savings have important implications for both policy formulation and firm management. For individual farms gains in efficiency are particularly in periods of financial stress. Efficient farmers are more likely to generate higher incomes and thus stand a better chance of surviving and prospering (Bravo-Ureta and Rieger, 1991).

A study on efficiency in artisanal fish production is important for many reasons. One, measuring efficiency of the producers and identifying the factors impacting on it will provide indications for the formulation of economic policies likely to improve producer efficiency and output in general. Two, at the micro-level, improved efficiency helps to increase the levels of income through increased profit and hence reduce poverty. Three, given the high costs of fish production and the low productivity, knowledge on technical efficiency levels will provide guidelines to government on how to improve output by farmers. Finally, whereas a number of studies have been undertaken on efficiency measurement in Artisanal fisheries (Squires *et al.*, 2003; Sesabo and Tol, 2005; Mahendra,2008;Oliveira *et al.*, 2010; Alam, 2011), to the best of my knowledge only Akanni(2008) has used stochastic frontier approach to measure technical efficiency of artisanal fisheries in Nigeria. Anene *et al.*, (2010) used production function to estimate resource use efficiency of artisanal fishing in Imo State of Nigeria.

In view of this it is pertinent to examine the technical efficiency of artisanal fisheries in Badagry Local Government Area of Lagos State of Nigeria.

Specifically, this study seeks to:

- (i) quantify the technical efficiency of the artisanal fisheries in the study area.
- (ii) examine the effects of socio – economic characteristics of farmers on technical efficiency
- (iii) determine the factors affecting artisanal fisheries in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Badagry Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State, Nigeria. Bagagry LGA is situated on the north bank of the main Lagoon, located around 6.5^o North of the equator and longitude 3.75^o East of the Greenwich Meridian. It is bounded in the south by the Atlantic Ocean, in the North by the Egbado territory, in the east hemmed in swampy water of Lagos and in the west by Benin Republic.

The population for this study is mainly artisanal fisher folks. This study made use of mainly primary data. The primary data were collected with the use of structured questionnaire which are administered on the farmers in the chosen areas of the study

Two state random sampling techniques was employed. Firstly, out of the eight fishing sites in the study are, three fishing sites were randomly selected. Secondly, forty artisanal fishermen were randomly selected from

each of the fishing site making a total of 120 farmers. The selected fishing sites are Alakotomeji, Yevoyan and Aivoji.

Model Specification

The stochastic frontier model adopted in this study is the variant of that of Khumbhakar and Heshmatic, 1995; Yao and Liu, 1998; and Ogundele, 2003. The model specified output (Y) as a function of input (X_i) and a disturbance term ()

$$Y_i = f(X_i, \beta) + v_i \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where Y_i is output by farmer i, X_i is input variables and β is a vector of parameters.

The disturbance term consist of two components,

$v_i = V_i - U_i$ where $V_i \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$ and U_i is a one – sided error term. The two errors, V_i and U_i are assumed to be independently distributed. The term V_i is symmetric, allows random variation of the production function across farms, and capture the effects of statistical noise, measurement error, and exogenous shocks beyond the control of the producing unit. The one – sided term, U_i represents technical inefficiency (TI) relative to the stochastic frontier. If $U_i = 0$, production lies on the stochastic frontier and production is technically efficient; If $U_i > 0$, production lies below the frontier and is inefficient.

The error term U_i is usually assumed to follow one of three possible distributions (Lee 1983; Schmidt and Lin, 1984 and Bauer, 1990); (a) half – normal i.e $N(0, \sigma_u^2)$; (b) Exponential $Exp(U_i, \sigma_u^2)$; and (c) truncated normal at zero $N(U_i, \sigma_u^2)$. Because the estimates of technical efficiency are similar for each distribution half – normal and truncated normal could be used. Following Jondrow *et al.*, (1982) technical inefficiency (TI) for each observation is calculated as the expected value of U_i condition on $v_i = V_i - U_i$

$$T_i = E\left(\frac{U_i}{\sigma_u}\right) = \sigma_u * \left[\frac{f^*(\lambda\varepsilon/\sigma)}{1-f^*(\lambda\varepsilon/\sigma)} - \frac{\lambda\varepsilon}{\sigma} \right] \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where f^* and F^* are, respectively the standard normal density and distribution functions, evaluated at $\lambda\varepsilon/\sigma$ and $\sigma^2 = \sigma_u^2 / \sigma_v^2 = \sigma_u^2 / \sigma_v^2$

Thus equation 1 and 2 provides estimates for U and V after replacing β, σ_u, and σ_v by their estimates. Subtracting V from both sides of (1) results in

$$Y^* = f(x_i, \beta) - u = Y - V \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where Y* is the firm’s observed output adjusted for the statistical noise captured by V.

Technical efficiency of an individual farmer is defined in terms of the ratio of the observe output to the corresponding frontier output, given the available technology.

$$\text{Technical efficiency (TE)} = \exp(-U_i) \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

The empirical model of the stochastic production frontier is specified as

$$\ln Y = \ln \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + V_i - U_i \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Where

- Y = Total output of fish (kg/year)
- X₁ = Family labour used (man-days)
- X₂ = Hired Labour used (man-days)
- X₃ = Cost of Repair
- X₄ = Cost of capital items (equipment)
- V_i = a random error term with normal distribution
- V ~ N(0, σ_v²)
- U_i = a non – negative random variables called technical inefficiency effects associated with technical inefficiency of production of farmers involved.

\ln = the natural logarithm (i.e. to base e)
 $B_0 - B_4$ = parameters to be estimated.

Inefficiency Effects and Socio – Economic Model

Average level of technical inefficiency measured by mode of truncated normal distribution (i.e. U_i) has been assumed (Kumbhakar and Heshmatic, 1995 and YaO and Liu, 1998) to be a function of socio – economic factors as shown in the relationship below.

$$U_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{edu}) + \beta_2(\text{Modoper}) + \beta_3(\text{Freq Fish}) \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Where

- Edu = years of schooling of the decision maker
- Modoper = mode of operation where 1 stands for full time and 2 for part – time.
- Freq = Frequency of fishing per week.

Estimation of the above model was accomplished through a joint estimation of the technical efficiency as specified by Coelli (1996).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Summary statistics for variables in the stochastic frontier model for the Artisanal Fisheries in Lagos State of Nigeria

Table 1 presents a summary statistics of variables used in the stochastic frontier production function. The mean output of fish in the study area is 12610.69kg. Both household and hired labours were extensively used by the respondents with a mean of 187.66 man-days and 225.19 man-days respectively. The mean cost of repair is N5550.25k and the mean cost of capital items (equipment) N85, 118.36k. This is so because an artisanal fishery is capital intensive. The mean year of schooling is 9.9years. This accounted for the high productivity and large profit from the enterprise. Most of the artisanal fishermen were full – time and the mean frequency of fishing is 5.94.

Maximum Likelihood Estimate of Frontier Model (MLEFM) for Artisanal Fisheries

The ordinary least square and the MLEFM are presented in table 2. The OLS estimate of the parameter for the production frontier has adjusted R^2 value of 0.83. This implies that the inputs used in the model were able to explain 83.4% of the variation in the output of fish in the study area. The coefficient of hired labour in man-days and cost of capital items are statistically significant at 1 percent level of significant and has expected signs. This implies that the more the use of this variables, the more the total outputs of fish in kg.

With an upward shift in the constant term, the coefficient of hired labour remained significant in the Cobb-Douglas stochastic frontier production function in the study area. From the ML estimates in Table 2, hired labour, repair and capital item equipment contribute significantly to the total output of fish in kg. Since the coefficients of the variables represent their corresponding elasticities, a coefficient of family labour of 0.36 means that artisanal fisheries output was in elastic with respect to family labour used. The coefficient of hired labour which means that fish output was elastic with respect to hired labour used. This elasticity implies that a 1 percent increase in the hired labour used in man-days, ceteris paribus would lead to an increase of 13.87% in the total output of fish. Though the use of equipments was found to contribute significantly to total output, the corresponding elasticity did not suggest that increased used of this input will yield more than proportionate increase in output.

The analysis of the inefficiency model shows that the signs and significance of the estimated coefficients in the inefficiency model have important implication on the technical efficiency of the farmers. The coefficient of years of education was positive and statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) indicating that this factor leads to a decrease in technical efficiency or an increase in technical inefficiency of artisanal fishermen in the study area. This finding is not in consonance with the earlier study by Akanni (2008) who reported positive and significant relation between education and efficiency in Lagos State. The coefficient of mode of operation is negative and statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) implying that this factor led to decrease in technical inefficiency. This indicates that full – time fishermen are more technically efficient than the part – time fishermen. Frequency of fishing also

has a negative coefficient and statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) implying that the more the frequency of fishing the more the technical efficiency.

The estimated sigma – squared (σ^2) is significantly different from zero ($p < 0.01$). This indicates a good fit and the correctness of the specified distributional assumptions of the composite error term. The estimated value of gamma parameter is 0.11, which means that 11% of the total variation in the total output is due to technical inefficiency.

Technical Efficiency (TE)

The predicted farm specific TE ranged between 0.698 and 1.00 with a mean of 0.921. Thus in the short run, there is a scope for increasing fish production by about 7.9% by adopting the technology and techniques used by the best practiced farmers. This result is higher than those obtained from other studies such as Squires *et al.*, (2003)(TE=84%); Sesabo and Tol, (2005)(TE=52%); Akanni, (2008) (TE=64.5%) and Alam, (2011) (TE=86%). The decile range of the frequency distribution of the TE is presented in Table 3. It shows that about 98.33 percent of the respondents had TE exceeding 0.69 and about 1.67% had TE ranging from 0.60 to 0.69.

CONCLUSION

The MLE result of the stochastic frontier production function reveals that hired labour, repair and capital items are the major factors influencing the total output of capture fish. Socio-economics factors such as years of education, mode of operation and the frequency of fishing of the artisanal fisheries have significant influence on the level of technical. The analysis also indicates that the level of technical efficiencies varies widely across farmers, ranging from 69.8 percent to 100 percent with a mean TE of 92.1 percent.

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Table1: Summary statistics of Variables of Artisanal fisheries

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Output (kg)	12610.69	10429.17	140	39186
Family labour(man – days)	187.66	234.79	0	728
Hired Labour (man – days)	225.19	314.22	0	1106
Cost of repair (₦)	5550.25	2541.33	1000	45657
Cost of Capital (₦)	85118.36	100199.82	3868	468492
Years of schooling	9.9	3.27	3	18
Frequency of Fishing	5.94	2.26	1	7

Source; Field Survey, 2008

Table2: Stochastic Frontier Production Functions on a sample of Artisanal Fishermen in Lagos State.

Variables	OLS	MLS
<u>General Model</u>		
Constant	3183.55(1.92)*	4655.88(19.55)***
Family Labour	0.14(0.35)	0.36(0.67)
Hired Labour	14.09(3.50)***	13.87(3.84)***
Repair	0.11(0.421)	0.53(6.17)***
Capital Items	0.04(5.34)***	0.04(7.28)***
<u>Inefficiency Model</u>		
Constant		4.75(1.25)
Years of Schooling		487.79(5.11)***
Mode of Operation		-901.10(-5.70)***
Frequency of Fishing		213.56(3.87)***
Sigma Square		6.87(6.87)***
Gamma		0.11(2.36)**
Log – likelihood function		-830.37
R ²	0.83	

Source: Field Survey, 2008

*, **, *** implies coefficient is significant at the 10%, 5% and 1% level of significance respectively.

Table3: Decile Range of Frequency Distribution of Technical Efficiency of Artisanal Fishermen

Decile Range of TE	Frequency	Percentage
0.60 – 0.69	2	1.7
0.70 – 0.79	10	8.3
0.80 - 0.89	12	10.0
0.90 – 0.99	94	78.3
1.00	2	1.7
Total	120	100
Mean	0.921	
Minimum	0.698	
Maximum	1.000	

Source: Field Survey,2008

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